

Bifid and Trifid Mandibular Canals: Are they Uncommon or Underestimated?

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ABSTRACT

Anatomical variations of the mandibular canal (MC) such as bifid MC (BMC) and trifid MC (TMC) have been largely reported in the scientific literature. They are characterized by two or three accessory canals running roughly parallel to MC. BMC and TMC are incidentally detected during routine dental radiography, and their thorough understanding is necessary to the practitioner to avoid complications during dental procedures. This paper aims to review BMC and TMC and to provide basic knowledge for dental clinical procedures.

KEYWORDS: Bifid, trifid, mandibular canal, panoramic radiograph, cone-beam computed tomography

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INTRODUCTION

The mandibular canal (MC) houses the inferior alveolar nerve, which is a branch of the mandibular nerve (the third division of the trigeminal nerve), and the inferior alveolar vessels [1]. It runs along the body of the mandible and terminates at the mandibular foramen on the medial aspect of the ramus [2]. MC can exhibit a circular, oval, or piriform shape [3].

Knowledge of MC anatomy and location is crucial for successful dental procedures, such as inferior alveolar nerve

block, implant placement, surgical dental extraction, especially wisdom teeth, etc. [4].

Anatomical variations of MC such as bifid MC (BMC) and more rarely trifid MC (TMC) have been reported in the scientific literature [5-10]. BMC and TMC are characterized by a canal with two (Figure 1) or three accessory canals running roughly parallel to MC [6, 10, 11]; these accessory canals result from ossification around minor branches, sometimes large enough, coming from the inferior alveolar nerve.

Figure 1: BMC as seen on the CBCT panoramic reconstruction, coronal and sagittal cuts. (Collection Dr. Ibrahim Nasseh)

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BMCs and TMCs do not have any clinical signs; they are fortuitously detected on conventional imaging techniques used in dental practice, such as panoramic radiography and cone-beam computed tomography (CBCT), which provides a more precise evaluation [10]. In fact, the panoramic 2D X-ray has limitations in exhibiting intraosseous structures such as MC, whose visibility may decrease when its borders become undetectable due to a poor bone density or a non-perpendicularity between the canal and the principal beam. Additionally, lesser resolution, elevated distortion, and the risk of phantom images are also main disadvantages of this technique.

This paper aims to review BMC and TMC and to provide basic knowledge for dental clinical procedures.

BIFID MANDIBULAR CANAL

BMC was evaluated by many authors by means of different radiographic techniques. Panoramic radiographs were used by Kalantar Motamedi et al. [12], Nortje et al. [6], and Langlais et al. [5], who found respectively a prevalence of 1.22% of BMC (61/5000), 0.91% (33/3612), and 0.95% (57/6000). In the same way, studies conducted by Grover and Lorton [13], Sanchiz et al. [14], and Kuczynski et al. [15] found that the prevalence of BMC was respectively 0.08% (4/5000), 0.35% (7/2012), and 1.98% (60/3024).

A higher incidence was reported by Miličević et al. [16] 4.66% (47/1008), Fuentes et al. [17] 11.02% (102/925) [16], and de Freitas et al. [18] 6% (30/500).

Nowadays, as imaging techniques like CBCT have advanced technologically, more details are provided, leading to better evaluation. Therefore, a number of studies suggest that using panoramic radiography alone underestimates the incidence of BMC [7, 11, 19]. Kuribayashi et al. believe that because panoramic radiographs are unable to detect all canals, particularly narrow ones, the incidence of BMC may be higher when utilizing CBCT. According to their study, 15.61% of people had BMC (47/301) [7]. Likewise, Klinge et al. [20], in their cadaveric study, found that panoramic images were unsuccessful to identify the MC in 36.1% of cases compared to CT scans, and Bogdán et al. [21] observed that on their sample of 46 dry mandibles, 9 BMCs (19.6%) were detectable, of which only 0.2% were visible on panoramic radiographs. On the other hand, on panoramic images, some anatomical structures may mimic BMCs, such as the groove of the mylohyoid nerve located on the deep medial surface of the ramus or some intra-bony dense trabecular formations [22-24].

Concerning the types of BMC, many classifications have been suggested by different authors, among others Nortje et al. [6], Naitoh et al. [25], and Langlais et al. [5], whose classification remains the most cited in the literature and divides BMCs into four types according to their locations and shapes (Table 1).

Table 1: BMC classification according to Langlais et al

Type of BMC	Description
Type 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Unilateral extending to the region of the third molar- Bilateral extending to the region of the third molar
Type 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Unilateral extending along the main canal and then coming together in the mandibular rami- Unilateral extending along the main canal and then coming together in the mandibular body- Bilateral extending along the main canal and then coming together in the mandibular rami- Bilateral extending along the main canal and then coming together in the mandibular body
Type 3	Combination between types 1 and 2
Type 4	Two canals from two distinct origins, and then joining to form a single, large MC

The BMC type that extends to the third molar region is the most common, according to many authors [26, 27].

TRIFID MANDIBULAR CANAL

TMC, which has been reported several years after BMC, is the second most commonly described mandibular canal variant in the scientific literature [22]. To date, many studies have been conducted on TMC prevalence using different methods and populations. In their assessment of 925 digital panoramic radiographs, Fuentes et al. [17] could not find any TMC. This is most likely because of the limitation of a two-dimensional imaging modality. On the other hand, Bogdán et al. found one case of TMC among the 46 dry mandibles they examined (2.17%) [21]. Similar prevalence (2.4%) was found by Okumuş and Dumlu, who investigated a sample of the Turkish population using CBCT [28]. Other studies assessed the MC anatomical variants in other populations, such as Rashuren et al. [29], who found 7 TMCs in 500 Korean patients (1.4%), and Yang et al. [30], who reported a prevalence of 1.1% among Han Chinese in Shanghai.

Similar to BMC, TMC was detected either unilaterally or bilaterally and in several mandibular locations [10].

CONCLUSION

Although they are regarded as uncommon anatomical variations, BMC and TMC can be found in any patient and need to be properly evaluated. Yet if routine panoramic radiographs are widely recommended before many dental and oral procedures, CBCT is considered more accurate for distinguishing true BMC and TMC from false positives.

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